

The Kinetics of Coagulation of Ceric Hydroxide Sol.

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Smoluchowski's equation (*Physikal. Z.*, 1916, 17, 557) for the kinetics of coagulation of a sol by electrolytes has been examined by several workers in the case of various sols. Mukherjee and Papaconstantinou (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1563; see also Mukherjee and Majumdar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 785) studied the coagulation of the gold sol by different concentrations of several electrolytes spectrophotometrically and found that the ratios $t_1 : t_2 : t_3 \dots$ where t_1, t_2, t_3 , etc., are the times since mixing of the electrolytes of various concentrations required for the sol to reach the same stage of coalescence, are to a certain extent independent of the stage of coalescence. Desai (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1928, 34, 181) also found in the case of the coagulation of thorium hydroxide sol that these ratios were fairly constant for certain concentrations of the coagulator.

The kinetics of the coagulation of the ceric hydroxide sol by electrolytes has been studied in the present investigation and samples of the sol dialysed and diluted to different extents have been used. The results obtained have been utilised for determining the conditions for observing the autocatalytic nature of the coagulation process.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the Sol.

The concentration of the sol prepared by dialysis of a solution of ceric ammonium nitrate changes with the progress of the dialysis and therefore, the sol, used in this investigation was prepared by precipitating ceric hydroxide from a solution of ceric ammonium nitrate with excess of ammonium hydroxide. The

precipitate was washed free from ammonia, suspended in distilled water and boiled. At intervals of a few minutes, two or three c.c. of 2N HCl were added to it and the mixture was stirred vigorously. By adding fresh water to the mixture from time to time the boiling was continued until a fluorescent golden yellow sol of ceric hydroxide was obtained. This sol was then continuously dialysed for several days and the samples of the sol were taken out whenever required. The colloid content of the sol was estimated by coagulating the sol by ammonium chloride, washing the coagulum free from chloride and weighing it as CeO_2 . The concentration of the sol was thus found to be 4.98 g. CeO_2 per litre and it remained constant during the entire period of dialysis. The coagulation velocity was followed by the thermopile method used by Mukherjee and Majumdar (*loc. cit.*). The ceric hydroxide sol is coloured yellow and on coagulation becomes dirty white; hence the sample of the sol, used for the coagulation experiments, was placed in an optical cell which served as the colour filter to cut off the light that would be absorbed by the sol prior to coagulation.

A mixture of 5 c. c. of the sol and 5 c. c. of distilled water was placed in the optical cell and the observed deflection gave the initial reading before the coagulation sets in. Then 5 c. c. of the sol were mixed with a solution of sodium or magnesium chloride which was made up to 5 c. c. by the addition of distilled water, and the time of mixing was noted. The mixing of the sol with the electrolyte was done in the same way throughout the investigation. The mixture was then transferred to the cell and the deflections of the galvanometer were noted at different intervals. Such observations were taken with the original sol as also with the sols diluted twice and four times with distilled water (sols A, A/2 A/4). The results obtained are shown in Figs. 1-6, in which the deflection differences ($D_i - D_t$), where D_i is the initial deflection and D_t , the deflection observed at time t after mixing the sol and the electrolyte, are plotted against t .

Curves 1—5 in Figures 1—3 refer to 450, 400, 350, 300 and 250 m. moles of NaCl per litre: curves 1—3 of Figures 4—6 refer to 8, 0.7 and 0.6 m. moles of NaCl.

FIG. 1.

Sol dialysed for 2 days (Sol A/2.)

FIG. 2.

Sol A/2

FIG. 3.

Sol A/4

FIG. 4.

Sol dialysed for 16 days.

FIG. 5.

Sol A/2

FIG. 6.

Sol A/4

DISCUSSION.

The coagulation velocity curves for sols A dialysed for 2 days are 'S' shaped and shown in Fig. 1. Those dialysed for 6 and 10 days are also similar. The nature of the curves is changed when the sol is

further dialysed (*cf.* Fig. 4). This has been observed to be the case when either sodium or magnesium chloride is used as the coagulating electrolyte. The 'S' shaped nature of the curve is also found to disappear when the sol dialysed for different days is diluted (*cf.* Figs. 2, 3, 5, and 6). It, therefore, appears that the 'S' shaped nature of the coagulation velocity curves is intimately connected with (i) the amount of the stabilising ions and (ii) the concentration of the colloid. These results are in agreement with those obtained by Patel and Desai (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 106, 128) on thorium hydroxide sol.

The 'S' shaped nature of the coagulation velocity curves can be explained as done by Patel and Desai (*loc.cit.*) on the first and the second critical potential of Freundlich. But Desai and co-workers have found that with the progress of dialysis, the charge on the particles of the gold and thorium and ferric hydroxide sols first increases, reaches a maximum and then begins to decrease. In view of these results it is apparent that the potential of the colloid particles will for some days of the dialysis increase and will cause a slowing down in the rate of coagulation. The coagulation velocity curves should, therefore, become more and more 'S' shaped. The measurement of the charge on the colloid particles with the progress of dialysis should, therefore, be made before the above explanation can be expected.

The values of t for the same stage of coalescence have been read from the coagulation velocity curves for sols dialysed for 2, 6, 10 and 16 days and coagulated by different amounts of the two electrolytes. The values of the ratio are given in the tables I-IV. It will be seen from the results that the values of the ratios T_n/T are nearly constant for sol dialysed for two days and coagulated by solutions of sodium and magnesium chlorides of different concentrations. However the deviations of the values of T_n/T from the mean increase as the concentration of the electrolyte is decreased and the sol is further dialysed (*cf.* Tables for 6, 10 and 16 days). It appears that in addition to the concentration of the coagulator, the stage of coalescence of the particles may be another important factor which determines the applicability of Smoluchowski's equation.

TABLE I

*Sol (A) dialysed for 2 days.**Sol (A) dialysed for 6 days.*

Deflection diff.	Conc. of NaCl in m. mols/litre.					Deflec- tion diff.	Conc. of NaCl in m. mols/litre.			
	450	400	350	300	250		62.5	56.25	50	43.75
	<i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₁ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₂ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₃ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₄ / <i>T</i>		<i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₁ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₂ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₃ / <i>T</i>
16	1	1.9	2.7	3.9	5.4	4	1	1.3	2.5	5.8
24	1	1.8	2.4	3.5	4.9	8	1	1.4	2.1	4.5
32	1	1.8	2.3	3.5	4.8	16	1	1.4	2.3	4.5
40	1	1.8	2.3	3.5	4.9	24	1	1.5	2.4	3.9
48	1	1.8	2.3	3.6	5.1	28	1	1.5	2.5	3.8
						32	1	1.6	2.6	4.1
						40	1	1.7	2.9	4.5
						48	1	1.5	2.8	4.7

TABLE II.

*Sol (A) dialysed for 10 days.**Sol (A) dialysed for 16 days.*

Deflection. diff.	Conc. of NaCl in m. mols/litre.				Deflection diff.	Conc. of NaCl in m. mols/litre.		
	13.75	12.5	11.25	10		8	7	6
	<i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₁ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₂ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₃ / <i>T</i>		<i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₁ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₂ / <i>T</i>
4	1	1.2	3.2	6.5	8	1	1.9	7.7
8	1	2.5	4.6	8.3	12	1	2.1	9.1
12	1	2.1	4.2	7.2	16	1	2.5	10.6
16	1	2.0	4.0	6.7	20	1	2.9	11.7
20	1	1.9	3.7	6.4	24	1	3.3	12.8
24	1	1.9	3.6	6.1	28	1	3.4	13.9
28	1	1.9	3.6	6.2	32	1	3.6	14.7

TABLE III.

<i>Sol (A) dialysed for 2 days.</i>				<i>Sol (A) dialysed for 6 days.</i>			
Deflection diff.	Conc. of MgCl ₂ in m. mols./litre.			Deflection diff.	Conc. of MgCl ₂ in m. mols./litre.		
	175 <i>T</i>	150 <i>T</i> ₁ / <i>T</i>	125 <i>T</i> ₂ / <i>T</i>		31·25 <i>T</i>	28·125 <i>T</i> ₁ / <i>T</i>	25·0 <i>T</i> ₂ / <i>T</i>
16	1	1·7	2·6	4	1	1·9	3·9
24	1	1·8	2·5	8	1	1·7	3·2
32	1	1·7	2·4	16	1	1·7	2·7
40	1	1·7	2·5	24	1	1·7	2·7
48	1	1·7	2·6	32	1	1·7	2·7
56	1	1·8	2·6	40	1	1·6	2·6
64	1	1·8	2·6				
72	1	1·9	2·7				
80	1	1·9	2·8				

TABLE IV.

<i>Sol (A) dialysed for 10 days.</i>				<i>Sol (A) dialysed for 16 days.</i>			
Deflection diff.	Conc. of MgCl ₂ in m. mols./litre.			Deflection diff.	Conc. of MgCl ₂ in m. mols./litre.		
	7·5 <i>T</i>	6·25 <i>T</i> ₁ / <i>T</i>	5·625 <i>T</i> ₂ / <i>T</i>		4·0 <i>T</i>	3·5 <i>T</i> ₁ / <i>T</i>	3·0 <i>T</i> ₂ / <i>T</i>
4	1	2·3	8·0	4	1	2·0	6·0
8	1	2·6	7·3	8	1	2·0	7·0
12	1	2·6	6·3	12	1	1·9	7·3
16	1	2·6	5·6	16	1	2·0	8·3
20	1	2·7	5·5	20	1	2·1	8·2
24	1	2·7	5·2	24	1	2·3	9·5
28	1	2·7	5·1				
32	1	2·8	5·1				

